

TEACHING ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES
(for businessman)

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Abstract: These days, a lot of areas are developing fast ,namely, marketing, business,engineering as well as interpreting. One of the main factors is the English language, as it is being the most prominent and well-accepted language of the world so that the people who know to speak in English are making profit easily. This article will give detailed information about learning English for different majors and the main purpose of learning for businessmen.

Keywords: business, major,specific,engineering,well-accepted, prominent, interpreting, factors, marketing,majors , businessmen.

Firstly right now , I am going to count why English is important and why we need to learn it.

1. English is a world language.English is the most widely spoken language in the world.
2. Learning English will help you get a job. English - science, aviation, computer, diplomacy and tourism.
3. Learning English helps to meet new people.English See the official language of 53 countries.
4. Many scientific works are written in English.In the 10th century, the number of scientific works written in English was greater than the number of articles written in the native language of the researcher.
5. English is the language of the media industry.Due to the popularity of

Hollywood in the world media, there are many pictures, TV shows and popular songs in English.

6. English is the language of the Internet. More than half of the content on the Internet is written in English.

7. It is much easier to travel with a good knowledge of English. Imagine if you are a Spanish person in Thailand, you can set your application administrator to answer the question in Spanish, but he can answer your question in English.

8. English is one of the most important languages for business. English is one of the most important business languages because it is the de facto language of the United States and the official language of the United Kingdom, Canada, India, and South Africa.

9. With English you can study all over the world. Because English is spoken in so many countries, there are thousands of schools and universities around the world that offer programs in English.

10. English provides access to multiple cultures. A good command of English will load you with films, music and literature from hundreds of countries around the world. Not to mention that many books around the world have been translated into English.

Why we need to use English in business?

Business English is very different from ordinary English. Special books help to learn business English - physical English, business and success, but also help to improve personal profit and quality of life. Learning English usually includes general language acquisition for life, travel, work, and a balanced study of formal and informal vocabulary, grammar, and all language skills. However, some people have special learning needs. Thus, a large layer of courses and programs appeared - English for specific purposes, covering not only business, but also medical, legal, IT, spoken English. Business English helps the student to focus on formal vocabulary and grammatical structures, to learn the cultural characteristics of

different countries, to learn the rules and customs of negotiations or presentations in other countries, and to acquire relevant knowledge for working abroad. First of all, it should be noted that books are only an auxiliary tool in learning business English. If you want to acquire fundamental knowledge, then it is better to take a comprehensive approach, in particular, take business English courses, consume English content in various formats - audio, video and print.

If you take time every day to focus on at least one of the four main components of the language (eg reading, writing, speaking and listening), you will improve your business English. However, learning a new language takes time. Four ways to learn business English; **Understanding:** Writing in English is considered an essential skill for success in today's global economy. As an English teacher, I write weekly journals and always use a dictionary to improve and expand my vocabulary.

Join a learning community.

Learning business English itself can be difficult and demotivating. Having a teacher or mentor can give you a friendly push, help you stick to your study plans, homework, and you can always ask for feedback! It's important to note that the best learning environment for working professionals is one that offers structured and flexible class schedules. This is something to consider. Plus, the bonus of joining a learning community means you'll have classmates you can hang out with. Classmates will also help you stay motivated and focused on homework.

Turning Your Free Time into Language Learning Opportunities .

An important skill you should start practicing is standing in front of a mirror and speaking. Have you ever wondered why boxers do shadow boxing? Shadow boxing is an exercise in which punches are thrown in the air. Used to warm up muscles before participating in physical activity. It sounds silly, but this exercise helps boxers develop muscle memory. Take this example of shadow boxing as a way to practice, just read some useful phrases in English in front of the mirror, it will help you improve your speech, delivery and most importantly, help you

remember the flow of words to speak naturally will give! This is a habit you should incorporate into your daily life because consistent practice develops learning habits that lead to long-term success.

What will happen if the salesman does not know English?

When you suggest to a non-native speaker that you have a deeper understanding of English in addition to your native language skills, it speaks volumes about your character and abilities. Your willingness to go above and beyond by learning a new language will show future employers and business partners that you can trust them to get you started. Your language skills can be your ticket to travel, securing an opportunity to serve your organization in an international market. Advanced business English skills are essential for high-level business negotiations, where first impressions are everything, and the subtleties of the language will easily set you back. If you are not fluent in business English, you may not notice the slight changes in grammar and syntax. Conventions and technical lingo are enough to follow, but the formalities of business English make it much more difficult to understand. Just a small misunderstanding can be the difference between losing millions of dollars or thousands of jobs, which is why we teach you to approach business English from a critical and analytical perspective. Doors will suddenly open when you can speak professionally using professional English. Knowing business English can bring you a big salary, a good name, and the life you've always dreamed of. These are the reasons why we need to learn the English language.

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